

Spirothiazolidones : Part I ; 5,5'-Spirobi-(2-Arylimino-4-Thiazolidones)

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In continuation of our studies on bisthiazolidones^{1,2} thirteen 5,5'-spirobi-(2-arylimino-4-thiazolidones) (Ia) and three 5,5'-spirobi-(2-arylimino-3-aryl-4-thiazolidones) (Ib) have been synthesized by refluxing dibromomalonic acid with corresponding arylthioureas in presence of fused sodium acetate in anhydrous ethanol.

Mercury derivatives of thiazoles³ and thiazolidones⁴ prepared earlier have been found to possess powerful antibacterial and fungistatic activities. Spirothiazolidones (Ia and Ib) have been mercurated using mercuric acetate to form acetoxymercuri thiazolidones. The assumption that the acetoxymercuri group enters the arylimino nucleus in compound Ia, is based on the reasoning advanced in our previous communication.⁴ In compound Ib, the acetoxymercuri group, however, enters both the arylimino-and N₃-aryl nuclei. The proof for this is obtained as follows. Compound Ia, when mercurated with mercuric acetate gave compound Ic containing two acetoxymercuri groups, whereas, compound Ib on mercuration under similar conditions yielded compound Id containing four acetoxymercuri groups. The number of acetoxymercuri groups was determined by the elemental analysis. On the basis of earlier observation^{5,6} on the mercuration of aromatic amines and phenols, it has been assumed that the acetoxymercuri group enters the para position of the orienting imino group and if this position is blocked, ortho substitution occurs.

The evaluation of bactericidal and fungicidal properties of spirothiazolidones and their mercuri derivatives is in progress. Melting points are uncorrected.

1. H. K. Pujari, *This Journal*, 1966, 43, 657.
2. H. S. Chaudhary and H. K. Pujari, communicated to *Indian J. Chem.*
3. M. K. Rout and H. K. Pujari, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 4507.
4. H. K. Pujari and M. K. Rout, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14B, 448.
5. Newton Friend, 'Text book of Inorganic Chemistry', (Charles Griffin, London), Volume XI, Part I, 1928.
6. S. S. Guha Sircar and M. K. Rout, *This Journal*, 1953, 30, 359.

Arylthioureas were prepared by boiling hydrochlorides of corresponding amines with ammonium thiocyanate according to the method of Declermont and Wehrlin⁷, and symmetrical diphenylthiourea (Riedal grade) and symmetrical ditolylthioureas (Fluka grade) were used.

5.5'-Spirobi-(2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone) (Ia, R₂ = C₆H₅): A mixture of dibromomalonic acid⁸ (1.31 g, 0.005 mol), phenyl thiourea (1.52 g, 0.01 mol) and anhydrous sodiumacetate (1.64 g, 0.02 mol) in absolute ethanol was heated on a water bath under reflux for 5 hr. After 2 to 3 hr heating, the reaction mixture became almost clear and assumed a light brown colour. It was then poured into ice-cold water and a pale yellow solid separated. The crude product was filtered, washed with hot water for 2-3 times to remove unused phenylthiourea and sodium acetate and finally recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 202°, yield, 44% (Found : S, 17.22 ; N, 15.08d : C₁₇H₁₃N₄S₂O₂ requires S, 17.40 ; N, 15.22%).

The properties and analytical data of the other spirothiazolidones are recorded in tables I and II.

TABLE I

Vide structure Ia

5,5'-Spirobi-(2-arylimino-4-thiazolidones)

No.	R ₂	Yield %	m.p. °C	% Sulphur		% Nitrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calcd.
2.	(o) H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	45	90	16.57	16.16	14.02	14.15
3.	(p) H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	40	120	16.18	16.16	13.88	14.15
4.	(m) Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	46	110	14.29	14.64	12.37	12.81
5.	(p) Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	32	145	14.62	14.64	12.56	12.81
6.	(m) MeO-C ₆ H ₄ -	56	89	14.63	14.95	12.86	1.30
7.	(p) MeO-C ₆ H ₄ -	56	202	14.58	14.95	13.12	13.08
8.	(p) Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	51	125	11.84	12.16	10.45	10.64
9.	(p) O ₂ N-C ₆ H ₄ -	31	212	13.61	13.97	18.12	18.34
10.	(3, 4) O ₂ N(Me)C ₆ H ₃ -	41	125 dec.	12.72	13.17	17.01	17.29
11.	(2, 5) Me(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₃ -	65	110	12.97	13.17	17.24	17.29
12.	α-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	56	95	13.25	13.67	11.48	11.97
13.	β-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	56	202	13.47	13.67	11.83	11.97

TABLE II

Vide structure Ib

5,5'-Spirobi-(2-arylimino-3-aryl-4-thiazolidones)

No.	R ₁ -R ₂	Yield %	m.p. °C	% Sulphur		% Nitrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
14.	C ₆ H ₅ -	50	119	12.05	12.30	10.54	10.76
15.	(o)H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	52	120	11.20	11.11	9.67	9.72
16.	(p)H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄ -	65	158	11.31	11.11	9.54	9.72

7. Ph. DeClermont and E. Wehrlin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, 31, 70 ; *Campt. rend.*, 1877, 88, 347.8. R. Willstätter, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 1375.

Mercuration of Spirothiazolidones: As the spirothiazolidones were soluble in alcohol-acetic acid solution with difficulty, mercuration of these compounds were affected by heating under reflux. A mixture of spirothiazolidone (0.0016 mol), mercuricacetate (1.2 g in 15 ml of water with 2-3 drops of dilute acetic acid) and 40-50 ml of ethanolacetic acid solution was refluxed on water bath for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured into a large volume of water with vigorous stirring and kept overnight to allow the precipitate to settle down. The precipitate was filtered, washed with hot water three times to remove mercuric acetate and finally purified by washing with dilute acetic acid and ethanol.

Table III and IV record the properties and analytical data of the mercury derivatives of spirothiazolidones.

TABLE III

Vide structure Ic

5,5'-Spirobi-(2-acetoxymercuri arylimino-4-thiazolidones)

No.	R ₂	Yield %	m.p. °C	%Hg.	
				Found	Calc.
17.	(<i>p</i>)AcOHgC ₆ H ₄ -	75	>300	45.04	45.25
18.	(<i>o, p</i>)H ₃ C(AcOHg)C ₆ H ₃ -	35	>300	43.62	43.86
19.	(<i>m, p</i>) Cl (AcOHg)C ₆ H ₃ -	65	230 dec.	41.85	41.98
20.	(<i>p, o</i>) Cl (AcOHg)C ₆ H ₃ -	70	252 dec.	41.92	41.98
21.	(<i>m, p</i>)MeO(AcOHg)C ₆ H ₃ -	50	240 dec.	42.06	42.37
22.	(<i>p, o</i>)MeO(AcOHg)C ₆ H ₃ -	50	250 dec.	41.93	42.37
23.	(<i>p, o</i>)Br(AcOHg)C ₆ H ₃ -	52	215 dec.	38.21	38.39
24.	(<i>p, o</i>)O ₂ N(AcOHg)C ₆ H ₃ -	58	>300	41.41	41.07

TABLE IV

Vide structure Id

5,5'- Spirobi-(2-acetoxymercuri arylimino-3-acetoxymercuri aryl-4-thiazolidones)

No.	R ₁ -R ₂	Yield %	m.p. °C	% Hg.	
				Found	Calc.
25.	(<i>p</i>)AcOHg.C ₆ H ₄ -	40	>300	51.34	51.34
26.	(<i>o, p</i>)H ₃ C(AcOHg)C ₆ H ₃ -	38	>300	49.55	49.75
27.	(<i>p, o</i>)H ₃ C(AcOHg)C ₆ H ₃ -	55	>300	49.84	49.75

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